

The Degree Of Administrative Creativity Of Public School Principals From The Point Of Teachers' View In Irbid Governorate Of Jordan

Athir Housni Al Kouri

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 03,2026</p> <p>Accepted: June 06,2026</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Administrative Creativity, Principals, Teachers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20572359</p>	<p><i>This research paper is about the degree of administrative creativity of public school principals from the point of teachers' view in Irbid Governorate of Jordan. Creativity is the process behind any progress and development of new ideas, which helps to enhance the expertise and competence of the creative person and achieve goals. Administrative creativity must be based on the individual's excellence in his vision of problems and their solution, and on his mental ability, intellectual fluency, and knowledge that can be developed in the presence of the appropriate climate and leadership on ability and interactive work relationships that develop the ability to reach new ideas and solutions in an innovative way. This intervention deals with the levels of creativity, the factors for achieving administrative creativity, and the characteristics of creative administrators.</i></p>

Introduction

Education contributes to building the human forces on which societies based in order to preserve their intellectual and cultural identity and to continue their progress in all fields. The preparation of a good citizen is one of the most important goals of contemporary education. The education sector is one of the most important sectors that affect and be affected by the administrative creativity of individuals in any society; The degree of administrative creativity practiced by school principals appears in the method of dealing, qualifying and developing teachers, so that it becomes a lived reality that positively or negatively affects society in general.

As for the school principal, who is one of the educational leaders concerned with his school affairs? The leadership style he follows often affects the quality of the educational process, and this may stem from the characteristics of that leader, who must be influential in the group's activity. Therefore, the school principal is consider as an educational leader. His job is with vital and very important tasks, and he has an effective role in improving the educational process. The success of the school in achieving its goals and mission depends on the style and method enjoyed by its principal, the leadership style that he practices, the successful leadership qualities that represented in his personality, and his ability to employ his potentials towards work. Building, in order to build positive human relations with workers, to improve working conditions (Al-Jami, 2014).

It is the responsibility of creative school principals to develop teachers' skills and outstanding abilities, and inspire them to do their best, develop their skills and upgrade their convictions, in order to reach advanced intellectual levels, raise the ceiling of their expectations, and motivate them to accomplish tasks that challenge their abilities to achieve the agreed goals, with constant attention. By providing the necessary feedback regarding their performance, and holding training courses to improve their cognitive, behavioral, professional, technical and other skills, because of their fundamental repercussions on the educational environment, as well as enhancing the teacher's self-confidence and motivating him to provide more for the advancement and advancement of the educational process (Reflianto, Ariani & Afrita , 2018).

The creative director constitutes the main key for the school's development and development. The principal's duty is to assist the school to produce creative ideas and direct them towards development and improvement. As well as employing his skills in designing plans that fit the desired goals, building a common vision, achieving excellence in performance and facilitating the process of solving problems, and imparting different experiences and skills to teachers. Focusing on administrative creativity, the principal is expected to create the basic principle and inspiring conditions for all members of the school with a higher level of leadership in order to improve the school environment, realize, confront difficulties, and get the school environment out of chaos (Yang, 2014).

Creativity is present and apparent to all managers, but they have it in varying degrees and in many areas, and it depends on the manager's ability to think, consider and reflect on matters from different angles and pillars. The idea has no value if it does not produce a result that serves the goal for which it designed, and the principal should be able to notice the contradictions and deficiencies in the school and surrounding environment.

Creativity is not only thinking about solutions, but also an awareness of the problems that arise, and an insight into the familiar and common from the perspective of Various (Burns, Machado, & Corte, 2015).

Administrative creativity concerns to instill confidence between managers and individuals who based on the educational process. Working to solve and end any problems or tensions between workers in educational institutions. The administrative creativity concerns increasing workers' confidence that managers are the biggest support for them and their new ideas and innovations by urging managers to follow administrative strategies which able to gain the confidence of employees in the educational institution, by honoring them, motivating them and involving them to make and implement decisions (Hafsi, 2018).

Administrative creativity is also one of the procedures used to develop and improve policies and methods of work and invent new mechanisms for the production of ideas. Stimulating brainstorming, employing the available human potential and benefiting from it in the optimal way and ways to achieve the goals as quickly as possible, by thinking in different ways to find different and individual ways, means and solutions that guarantee progress, improve outcomes and develop capabilities that lead to success (Kodama, 2017).

Administrative creativity is an important factor in the progress and quality of educational institutions' outputs, and it continuously improves administrative strategies and is able to adapt to all changes of this era. Administrative creativity helps to discover and refine the skills and capabilities of individuals involved in the educational process and to increase its quality and flexibility. In addition to its great importance in enhancing confidence and motivation in the hearts of individuals working in educational institutions and directing them towards developing new teaching methods that serve the educational process and raise its efficiency (Hewison & Holden, 2016).

Administrative creativity is one of the most important capabilities that characterized by administrators to achieve unity and integration among individuals in an organization. Where it instills the spirit of innovation in the completion of work efficiently and with high skill, in addition to its importance in solving problems and dealing with developments in positive and effective ways. In addition to the importance of administrative creativity in instilling motives and constructive ideas necessary for development, progress, achieving goals and increasing the enthusiasm of individuals for work. Administrative creativity helps to develop effective organizational methods and strategies capable of achieving the desired goals (Pavlov, 2016).

The presence of a school administration represented by the school principal, who seems as a representative of the authority with his leadership behavior and morals, is a vital element in the performance and organization of the school, as the roles of school administration have changed and expanded. Rather, it has become concerned with everything related to the educational process, including students, teachers, teaching methods, school activities, and strengthening the relationship with the local community (Al-Qar'an & Al-Harashah, 2011, 25).

The Importance of the Research Paper:

The importance of this research paper comes from the urgent need for school principals to practice administrative creativity and to apply it in practice on the ground, which motivates teachers, raises the level of their morale and improves their performance level.

Objectives of the Research Paper:

This research paper aims to reach the best practical results for managing creativity by school principals, by identifying the most important practices of administrative creativity among school principals because of their significant impact on the educational environment.

The problem:

The central problem of this research paper revolves around "the degree of administrative creativity of public school principals from the point of teachers' view in Irbid Governorate of Jordan". Where it assumed that there should be a creative administration and has an accurate plan to solve the problems it faces. Develop a future vision for the advancement of the school. The weakness of the practice of school principals Administrative creativity and the failure to use modern administrative methods, and the managers' lack of awareness of the problems and crises in the educational environment in a timely manner, which reflected in their ability to manage planning processes and produce new ideas and translate them into tangible actions.

This research paper will seek to clarify the degree of administrative creativity practiced by school principals in Irbid Governorate from the teachers' point of view, and the questions that arise, what is the concept of administrative creativity? What are the levels of administrative creativity? What are the factors for achieving administrative creativity? What are the characteristics of creative administrators? This is what will clarify in this research paper.

Previous Studies:

Crum and Sherman (2008) conducted a study that aimed to know the impact of the administrative, leadership and educational creativity of secondary school principals on developing the performance of workers in Virginia state schools in the United States of America. The study sample consisted of (100) school principals and the questionnaire that was developed was used. For this study and the study concluded that the success of

secondary school principals in achieving an advanced level among their students is due to the creative administrative practices resulting from creating a supportive environment for the achievements of their employees.

The study of Tayari & Tavakoli (2015) aimed to determine the relationship between creativity and organizational innovation among principals and teachers of secondary schools for girls in Iran. The descriptive correlative approach was used, the study tools were developed to collect the two data from the study sample in the form of groups from all schools that belong to the study, and the results of the study showed a strong relationship between creativity and innovation for teachers and administrators according to the Pearson correlation coefficient (0.409).

Phimphon, Tesaputa & Somprach (2015) conducted a study aimed at developing and strengthening the creative leadership program among school principals in Lagos, Thailand. The results were evaluated after implementing the program and to achieve the purpose of the study. A questionnaire was used that was distributed to (179) A school in Lagos is divided into three levels: principals, deputy principals and heads of departments. One of the findings of the study is that the level of flexibility and creativity was at a low degree among the first sample group, and after implementing the creative leadership program among the principals of those schools, the results reached a significant increase as it was prior to implementation.

The study of Abdul-Aal and Saleh Al-Shammri (2018) aimed to know the reality of administrative creativity for secondary school administrations in the city of Sohag. The results of the study showed that the administrations of secondary schools in Sohag applied the elements and aspects of administrative creativity at a low level. The results of the study also revealed the most important obstacles that can limit the administrative creativity of the administrations of these schools, the application of centralization in them and the weakness of giving powers to teachers.

Successful educational leadership requires accuracy, flexibility and effort. Through it, the school principal confirms his leadership role, through what he can do efficiently in dealing with educational situations that appear from time to time, and his high ability to invest these situations within his school and its employees and transform them from situations Destructive to positive attitudes that develop and improve the educational process within the school. When considering and delving into all of the above, and what the previous studies and efforts confirmed of the importance and effectiveness of the administrative creativity style in the educational process and its main role in the development of educational institutions.

The Concept of Managerial Creativity:

The concept of creativity considers as one of the flexible concepts that accommodates many opinions, and it is one of the most controversial topics. The creativity is a very complex human phenomenon with many kinds, where creativity is one of the mental advantages that distinguish man from other creatures. This helped the human advantage over survival, development and construction, in addition to the great importance of creativity in solving the problems facing individuals and societies with high efficiency to reach the highest levels of adaptation, development and well-being (Shaheen, 2018).

It is the creation of new and effective ways of thinking that capable of bring all new things by excelling in understanding matters and the ability to provide unprecedented solutions to problems, and innovating methods, and strategies that reach new superior distinct results. To see the familiar in a new and unfamiliar way and to accomplish work and duties in an elaborate manner and dedicated to achieving superior and satisfactory results. (Mulet, Royo, Chulvi, & Galan, 2017).

Al-Hadhrami and Al-Shawamin (2017) define administrative creativity as a cognitive mental process through which the school principal interacts with both the organizational and public environments, in order to transcend and move away from the familiar and search for what is new and innovative and at the same time able to meet the needs of all parties and bring them benefit.

Marei (2014) believes that administrative creativity is the initiative shown by the school principal to deviate from the familiar and traditional in the school and advance it to be full of creativity and innovation.

Administrative creativity is defined as a set of practices and processes applied by school principals during their work period, which require them to find the most appropriate and most efficient and effective methods and methods in search that are distinct from the traditional methods and to achieve the goals of the school at the same time (Al-Saudi, 2012, 14).

Creativity Levels:

Al-Amyan (2005) reported that creativity appears on many levels, including what is at the level of the individual. Creativity reaches by an individual and from the innate characteristics characterized by curiosity, perseverance, self-confidence, independence in judgment, self-assertion, intelligence, flexibility, love of risk, ambition and ability On analysis, and creativity at the group level. It is reached by the work group that cooperates among themselves to implement their ideas and change for the better, and creativity at the level of the institution. He considered it the product of the cooperative effort of all members of the institution, in which the institution is characterized by field orientation and tendency towards practice and experimentation and encouraging creators and guide them.

Administrative Creativity:

Al-Serafy (2006) mentioned five levels of administrative creativity:

- a. Expressive creativity: It means the traditional way in which a person who practices a profession or work is distinguished.
- b. Artistic creativity: It is represented in the aesthetic aspect that is added to goods and services, such as decorative works that are added to service places.
- c. Invention: It means creating something new for the first time by modifying its previously constituent parts so that they take a new path, such as the developments witnessed by the computer.
- d. Complex creativity: It is the collection of different ideas to bring them to new information.
- E. Developments: It is represented in using something that already exists and re-developing it and building on it again in order to be applied in new fields.

Factors for Achieving Administrative Creativity:

Many factors can stimulate creativity among creative individuals and groups to produce new ideas that are able to improve the educational process, improve its outputs and advance it. Achieving scientific and intellectual development and progress and bringing about positive changes. Where these factors can be divided into the following (Al-Nasser & Hussein, 2018):

- a. **Directive and Supervisory Encouragement:** It means the support in addition, familiarity that the creative person receives from the principals and supervisors in charge of the educational process. By making the creators aware of their great importance and enhancing their self-confidence.
- b. **Organizational Support:** It is intended to support the creators working in the organization by supporting and adopting new ideas. Notifying the creative person that he is an important, effective and important individual in the organization and providing them with support in any circumstance.
- c. **Workgroup Characteristics:** It means creative and distinguished individuals who are able to produce new ideas and who are present in the work environment. It helps these individuals support, motivate and develop their colleagues.
- d. **Challenge:** It means internal motivation, determination, and determination to produce ideas capable of reviving the educational process and improving its outcomes. This incentive works to release the latent energies of the creative person and direct it towards generating new ideas (Hafez, 2011).

Characteristics of Creative Administrators:

The administrative leader who has the ability to bring about renewal represents the cornerstone of the administrative innovation path. This leader has many features and characteristics, which are as follows:

1. **Cognitive Characteristics:** Some of the cognitive characteristics of creative individuals appear, such as the arithmetic ability, the ability to deal with abstract words and symbols and use them correctly, curiosity, the desire to learn about the surrounding environment, and independence at work, as the individual tends to work alone to be able to build an integrated picture of the problem. And his ability to maintain his orientation towards the proposed problem to perfect its solution, regardless of the strength of the distractions that try to keep him away from the original problem, and the linguistic ability, as they tend to love reading and reading various and in-depth books (Al-Huwaidi, 2007, 45).
2. **Emotional Characteristics:** they are represented in the enjoyment of wise leadership that possesses strength and control, commitment to the national duty towards the school, tendency to take risks, accept ambiguity, self-control, non-compliance with regulations and instructions, freedom from self-restrictions, benefit from crises and turn them into opportunities and strive hard to reach successful results. He avoids failure and enthusiasm for his ideas and their implementation, and enjoys the spirit of initiative and openness to new experiences, daring to express opinions and attention to the opinions of others (Younis, 2000).
3. **Mental Characteristics:** They are represented in the ability to produce the largest amount of ideas in a specific time, flexibility in thinking, and the ability to change the direction of thinking easily, so that it can adapt to changing circumstances, and the ability to organize ideas into broader and more comprehensive patterns, and permanently out of the ordinary. And relying on divergent thinking, and independence in thinking (Al-Ajeez & Sheldan, 2010).

Recommendations

Through this presented research paper, a number of important recommendations can be reached to achieve quality performance:

- 1- School principals seriously adopt creative practices in their work, which affect performance, conflict resolution methods and the development of the educational institution.

- 2- Granting school principals in Irbid governorate powers and easing restrictions in instructions that impede the practice of administrative creativity in the field of work.

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Author Information

Athir Housni Al Kouri – PHD.

Management Educational – Yarmouk University
English Teacher - Al Bahrinia School - Irbid –
Jordan
